

DNA Replication & DNA Repair

absent:

Phylum	Species
Cryptophyte	<i>Cryptomonas paramecium</i>
	<i>Hemiselmis andersenii</i>
	<i>Chroomonas mesostigmatica</i>
	<i>Guillardia theta</i>

Phylum	Species
Chlorarachniophyte	<i>Bigelowiella natans</i>
	<i>Lotharella vacuolate</i>
	<i>Amorphochlora amoebiformis</i>

Replisome

Double strand break repair

Endonucleases

Nucleomorphs